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Śaivism in the Undivided Balasore District of Odisha

Dr. Anil Kumar Acharya¹

Abstract

Undivided Balasore, comprising the present Balasore and Bhadrak districts, is a flourishing coastal area of Odisha. In this coastal region of Odisha, at present, there exists an amalgamative Hindu religious trend, mostly influenced by Vaisṇavism, Śaivism, Tāntrism, etc. Because of that, it is somewhat difficult to correctly define the present trend of 'Śaivism proper' in this region. Śaivism seems to have survived mostly in the form of popular temple worship of laymen. Therefore, an attempt has been made herein to present an apparently comprehensive picture of Śaivism pertaining to this district, documenting the existing ancient monuments and places of historical importance. Herein the intent is not to present some new findings pertaining to the Śaivism of this place; rather, to comprehend the available facts in a single paper and revisit the past glory of Śaivism in this region.

Key Words: Śaivism, Bāṇāsura, Balasore, Odisha, Lakuliśa

Undivided Balasore, comprising the present Balasore and Bhadrak districts, is a flourishing coastal area of Odisha with a history of different religions, viz. Buddhism, Jainism, Śaivism, Śāktism, and Vaisṇavism, etc., as could be seen in other parts of Odisha. At present, there exists an amalgamative religious trend, mostly influenced by Tāntrism and Vaisṇavism, because of which it is somewhat difficult to correctly define the present trend of 'Śaivism proper' in this coastal district of Odisha; however, a 'Śaivaite proper' has been characterized: "*The orthodox devotees mark three horizontal*

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lines of sandalwood paste² on their forehead as religious mark and were Rudrakshya mala round their neck to identify their sect (Behuria 128)”. In this present trend of the Hindu religion of this region, Śaivism stands perhaps next to Vaiṣṇavism. Also, it is very rare to see any ‘Śaivaite proper’ and difficult to trace a manual of ‘Śaivaite proper’ in this district; rather, Śaivism seems to have survived mostly in the form of popular temple worship of laymen. Therefore, present herein an apparently comprehensive picture of Śaivism pertaining to this district, documenting the existing ancient monuments and places of historical importance. Herein do not intend to present some new findings pertaining to the Śaivism of this place; rather, to comprehend the available facts in a single paper.

Whenever Śaivism comes into question, residents of Balasore never forget to glorify the five Śiva temples of his district, viz. Bāṇeśvara in Puruṇābāleśvara (old town of Balasore), Gargeśvara (popularly known as Gaḍagaḍeśvara) in Purusottampur of Remuṇā block, Kharjuresvara in Seragaḍa, Pañcalingeśvara in Nilgiri municipality and Maṇināgeśvara in Bardhanpur village of Rasālpur block. It is a popular belief that all these five temples were built by certain Bāṇa Rājā, whom people connect with Bāṇāsura the puranic character. In identification of this Bāṇa Rājā Dr. N. N. Vasu has opined that “*There was, in Deccan, a dynasty of Bāṇa Rājā. The earliest records left of this dynasty are some inscriptions, belonging to the tenth century of the Christian era. Kings of this dynasty waged war against the Chola and Ganga Rājās. Parāntaka Chola conquered the kingdom of Bāṇa and gave it to Prthivipati the second of the Ganga dynasty (Epigraphia Indica, Vol.III, pp.142).* The ancient Śaivaite temples of Bāṇeśvara were most probably built under the orders and supervision of the kings of Bāṇa dynasty. As in the Deccan, the Ganga kings conquered the kingdom of the Bāṇa Rājās, so it is probable, that here too the ascendancy of the Bāṇa Rājās passed away with the rise of Ganges (Vasu 1911, 100-101)”. In a succeeding section, while dealing with the Maṇināgeśvara temple, the same author mentioned that – “*The ancient temple of Maṇināgeśvara was destroyed by Muhammadans. About sixty years ago, the late Bābu Bhagavān Dās of Balasore, a zamindar of this place, had this*

2 It is to be noted that the usual material for tripuṇḍra, i.e. three horizontal lines on forehead, is bhaṣma, i.e. ash made of holy cow dung.

temple repaired (106)". And he has concluded with the assumption that, since the figure of the goddess Kamalā or Gaja-Lakshmi on the upper portion of the doorway of that temple is exactly similar to the figure of Kamalā found on the coins of the Gupata kings of Gauda, therefore, "*the original temple of Maṇināgeśvara was built under the order of some Gupta king [of Gauda] or of some Hindu chief under the suzerainty of the Gupta kings (107)*". But a significant remark pertaining to the Maṇināgeśvara temple has been recorded in the Gazetteers of Baleshwar district: "*the architectural features of the temple give adequate information that it was constructed in the 11th century A. D., by Bhanja rulers (Behuria 765)*". Also with reference to the Bāṇeśvara temple of Puruṇābāleśvara John Beams has opined: "*The little village of Balasore which afterwards, under English influence, grew into the present town, is called from a temple to Mahadeva Vanesvara or "Shiva the forest lord," probably because the place where his temple stood was covered by dense jungles(Sahu et al., vol. 2).*" Therefore logically, the popular notion 'Bāṇāsura built these temples' could not be accepted; however, considering the fact: "*Banasura ruled in present-day central Assam with his capital at Sonitpur (present-day Tezpur, Assam)*" ("Banasura"; Veṭṭaṃmāṇi), Bāṇāsura's influence in this north-eastern border district of Odisha in ancient time could not be completely discarded, because some sort of indirect relation of Bāṇāsura and Assam with Odisha could be traced in epics and purāṇas, which will be discussed due section of this article.

The above-mentioned remarks, cited from different sources, suggest the difficulty in dating these temples; however, those remarks certainly point towards a sequence of time, i.e. period of Bāṇāsura, the mythological character (Early History) → Gupta kings of Gauda (4th – 6th century A.D.) / Bāṇa kings of South-India (middle of 4th to as late as 13th & 15th century A.D.)³ → Bhaṇja kings (11th century A.D.) → dilapidate temple surrounded by dense forest/ destroyed by Mugals (16th - 18th century A.D.) → repaired by local *Zamindars* (19th century A.D.).

Regarding the kings of different dynasties assumed to be associated with the building of these 'Bāṇāsura group of temples': –

3 "Banas are mentioned in Tamil Nadu as late as 13th and 15th century."-
Wikipedia

Nothing could be said firmly about the epic-fame Bāṇāsura, the king of central Assam. However, some traces of the relationship of Bāṇāsura and Assam with Odisha, which have been pointed out by scholars, could be taken into consideration. Regarding the origin of Kaliṅga, the ancient constituent of present Odisha, it has been observed by Dr. Harekrushna Mhatab that in the Ādiparva of Mahābhārata and in Brahmāṇḍapurāṇa it has been recorded that “*Under the ancient levirate custom, five sons were born to Queen Sudeshṇā, wife of Vali[Bali], by the sage Dirghatamah. These five sons were Aṅga, Vāṅga[Vaṅga], Kaliṅga, Puṅdra and Suhma. Subsequently the regions ruled by these five were named after each of them*” (Mahtab). And according to the genealogy of Bāṇāsura he is the son of Bali or Mahābali. Also, it has been mentioned in the Mahābhārata that “*During the battle of Kurukshetra, the Kaliṅga army was lead by Bhagadatta, the King of Kāmaruṇa [i.e. Assam]*” (10). Therefore Bāṇāsura and Assam are indirectly related to Odisha and this Bāṇāsura might have played some role in the propagation of Śaivism in this coastal district of Odisha.

Guptas’ direct sway over Odisha is still a disputed point despite their widespread influence observed in the Odishan monuments. And in spite of the influence of the Guptas, indirectly through the Guptas of Gauda, observed in one of the figures of the above-mentioned temple, it would not be correct to connect those temples with Guptas, because it has been opined that “*The Guptas were Vaishṇavas and naturally they patronized Vaishnavism in Orissa during their rule*” (Mahatab 508). If at all the connection of a Gauda king is to be assumed then probably the best would be the great Saivite King named Shashanka (7th century A.D.), who established his own kingdom after the death of the Gupta king of Gauda named Mahasengupta and information regarding him has been mentioned in the copperplates of his vassal Madhavavarma, the king of Ganjam (Odisha).

Bāṇa kings were present in various parts of Andhra and Tamilnadu. Therefore, their influence in the southern parts of Odisha is reasonable; but to connect them with these temples of the *northeastern* border district of Odisha seems inappropriate, especially in the absence of any evidence and between Bāṇāsura

of Assam and Bāṇas of South, the former is nearer to this part of Odisha than the latter.

At last, only Bhañjas remain in question and their connection with these temples seems relatively the best possibility because they are the native Śaivaite kings of Odisha and were ruling the neighboring Mayurbhanj district. Therefore, as quoted above, Bhañja king's connection with one of these 'Bāṇāsura group of temples' has been attested in the Gazetteer of India.

Besides, it would not be out of context to remember the Māna kings of Uttara-Tosali, who have styled themselves as *Paramamāheśvara* (a great devotee of Maheśvara), and were present in a Visaya or district called Sarephahara, i.e. modern Soro, and Mahārājā Śrī Gaṇa of the Bhadrakali stone inscription discovered at Bhadrak. Therefore, I am inclined herewith to suggest that 'Bāṇa' in connection with the five temples of Balasore could be a corruption (*apabhraṃśa*) of 'Māna' or 'Gaṇa'; but not quite sure about this.

Besides the confusion attested in the above discussion, the ancientness of these temples is beyond any doubt, though bear scantily any token of ancientness, except in popular notion. The reason behind the unavailability of any token of ancientness may be the Muslim invasion, which is evident from the above-mentioned statement of Dr. Vasu on Mañināgeśvara temple. The same might have been the case with other temples. Therefore, these undated monuments point towards the deep devotion of the rulers of Balasore to Lord Śiva.

Besides the above five temples, there is another Śiva temple in Chandaneśvara, a small town near the border of Odisha and West Bengal. It is one of the popular Śiva temples of these days. "*Candaneswar Mahadeva temple built in Gaudiya style with a series of dome-shaped chambers. The zamindar of Panchetgarh took initiative and built the present shrine through the financial assistance of the local people*" (Behuria 774-775). Also, the colossal Śivalinga named Bhubaneśvara / Bhuṣaṇḍeśvara found in Kumbhīrgari (Kirtania) in Bhogarai area of Balasore is an important Śaiva monument. "*The Sivalinga is made of well polished black chlorite stone and is designed in three separate sections. The total height of the Linga is about 3.6576 meters (twelve feet). The upper most part measuring about 1.2192*

meters (four feet) in cylindrical shape contains a line of carving which the local people consider as the sacred thread of the deity. The middle portion measuring about 1.2192 (four feet) is in octagonal shape. The lower portion, i.e. the base of the Sivalinga is in square plan. The circumference of the sakti is about 9.144 meters (30 feet) with measure 1.8288 metres (six feet) in each side and its depth is 0.6096 meter (2 feet) at the most” (779-780)

There are a few important places often remembered in connection with Śaivism, though not exclusively, in Balasore. They are Soro and Ayodhyā.

- 1) Soro – This place is often remembered in the context of the fusion of Buddhism and Śaivism in Odisha. Śivalinga inscribed with the Buddhist *dhāraṇī*⁴ found from Gohirāsāhi of Soro is of great interest to scholars. Scholars, viz. S. C. De, L. K. Panda, Donaldson, etc., have reflected enough on this monument. This monument could be roughly dated between the 8th and 10th century A.D., because Donaldson, citing S. C. De, has opined that “Śiva-linga with the Buddhist *dhāraṇī* “Om ye dharmā hetu prabhavā he ...” inscribed on four sides of its square pedestal, paleographically assignable to the late 9th or early 10th century A. D” (Donaldson 33) And L. K. Panda, in his book *Śaivism in Orissa*, has discussed this monument under the period of ‘Ascendancy of the Bhaumakaras’, i.e. 8th century A.D and has opined: “Palaeographically, the inscription is to be placed after the Neulapur Copper Plate of Śubhakaradeva” (Panda 61) Regarding the fusion of religion which this monument reflects Donaldson, citing S. C. De, has mentioned: “He [S. C. De] suggests that the *dhāraṇī*, by this time, “had lost its significance as a Buddhist one and came to be regarded as a mantra used for inscriptions on an image, Buddhist or Brahmanical. It is about the period when Buddhism in Odisha was in the process of assimilation by the

4 *Dhāraṇī* is “a magical prayer, or merely a conglomeration of Syllables for the purpose of casting spell.”- Donaldson, Thomas Eugene, *Iconography of the Buddhist sculpture of Orissa*, 2 Vols., IGNC & Abhinav Publications, New Delhi, 2001, p.422; The prayer is: “Om ye dharmāhetu prabhava hetuṃ teṣāṃ tathāgato hyavedat tośascha (teṣāṃ cha)[teṣāṃ] ca yo nirodha evaṃ vadi mahāśramaṇaḥ” - Panda, Lakshman Kumar, *Saivism in Orissa*, Sundeeep Prakashan, New Delhi, 1985, p.61

Brahmanical faith.” Buddhism, however, was still quite strong and popular at this time and, contrary to the opinion of S. C. De, the *linga*, with a band of scrollwork running around the shaft near the base, certainly does resemble a monolithic *stūpa*” (Donaldson 340).

L. K. Panda has viewed differently: “*This palaeography suggests that in the eighth century the Śaiva Acharyas allowed the incorporation of the mystic Buddhist formula of dhāraṇī in the rituals of Śaiva shrines*” (Panda 62)

From the above-mentioned citations, it is clear that the Śivalinga inscribed with *dhāraṇī* is a pre-twelfth-century monument showing the fusion of Buddhism and Śaivism in Odisha.

- 2) Ayodhyā [colloquially Ajodhyā] – This is a place of greater interest to an antiquarian. This is a relatively big village, which “*was once the capital of the Vairāṭa-rājās. The River Ghargharā flows to the east and the south, the Sona (Suvarna) to the north and the Sindhu, to the west of the village. It is called Ayodhyā, because the Ghargharā flows by its side just as a river of the same name flows by of Ayodhyā, the celebrated capital of the Kings of Solar dynasty*” (Vasu 87). Uttareśvara Mahādeva temple and Khuṇṭiā temple are two existing Śaiva shrines built by Bhānu Khuṇṭiā, on the foundation of old temples, in the 19th century; besides, ruins of an old Kurumberā and Śiva temple are found in front of the temple of Mārīchi Thākuraṇī, which was built by Bhānu Khuṇṭiā in 19th century. Also, it has been mentioned by Dr. Vasu that “*Small images of Hara and Pārvatī have also been discovered at the time of making excavations near Mārīchi Naṭā,*” (90) the ancient site of Mārīchi temple. From the abundance of Buddhist sculptures found in this area, one could tend to believe that Buddhism must have flourished here in earlier times than Śaivism as the same order has been observed in other places of Odisha. Therefore Dr. Vasu has opined that “*Śaivism became prevalent here after the Tāntrika Buddhist period [10th – 11th century A.D. relevant to this particular place].*” (90-91)

Lastly, a very important monument that testifies to the ancientness of Śaivism in Balasore is a statue of Lakulīśa, which was excavated from Kasbā [also known as Kaspā]. I came across this sculpture, which was

described as “Buddha practicing yoga”, during the period of reading the book *Archeological Survey of Mayurabhanja* by N. N. Vasu, but my mind, which had till that time remembered many images of Lakulīśa from the temples of Bhubaneśvra, did not accept the identification of Dr. Vasu and was enthusiastically inclined to identify it as an image of Lakulīśa. In suspicion of the existence of any literature that would have proven the same, which I was independently thinking about, I searched some literature and finally got the latest publication by Donaldson, in which he has also identified the image in question as Lakulīśa and has referred: “*The image of Lakulīśa from Kasbā, now in the compound of the Fakirmohan college at Balasore, for example, was identified as Buddha by N. N. Vasu*” (Donaldson, p.433, reference no. 58) Also, the same sculpture has been mentioned as Lakulīśa in the Odisha District Gazetteers, Baleshwar, in *Gazetter of India*, 1994 (p. 763). In fact, this incident of the identification of Lakulīśa supplies the inspiration for undertaking an effort to pen down this article.

This image of Lakulīśa is seated on *viśvapadma* in slightly raised crossed legs tied around with *yogapaṭṭa*. Hands exhibit the *dharmacakrapravartana-mudrā*. The *lkuṭa* (club), the essential sign of Lakulīśa image, is held between the left arms. The ear lobes are dilated and hair is arranged in snail-shell curls, and most importantly this image is marked with *ūrdhvalinga* (with erect linga), a distinguished feature mentioned: “*In the Viśvakarmāvatāra-vāstu-śāstra manuscript of the Deccan College Library is a verse which specifies that Lakulīśa should be represented ūrdhva-linga (with erect linga)...*” (390) In this regard, it could be remembered that the Lakulīśa image of Vaitāla temple (as shown in K. C. Panigrahi’s book: *Archaeological Remains at Bhubaneswar*, fig. 126) is also marked with *ūrdhvalinga*. This image has been flanked by four minor images, two each arranged on either side, seated on a lotus whose stalk is issued from the *viśvapadma* of the main image i.e. Lakulīśa. Four minor images, usually considered as four disciples of Lakulīśa viz. Kauśika, Garga, Mitra, and Kaurushya, are presented in an apparently younger appearance without bearded faces and the seating posture of all four minor images is different from each other, but the gesture of all minor images seems to be alike i.e. listening. This image has been dated between the 8th – 9th century A.D. by Donaldson, who

has taken this sculpture as an example of one of the earliest images of Lakuliśa by referring to this image while narrating the Buddhist influence on the early images of Lakuliśa. He says: “*On most early images his ear-lobes are distended, his hair is arranged in snail-shell curls neatly aligned in rows and he has a cranial protuberance, features suggesting the influence of Buddhism (fig. 499) [this number refers to the image of Lakuliśa from Kasbā given in his book ‘Iconography of The Buddhist Sculptures of Orissa’, Vol.II (plates)]*” (390)

From the above discussion, it is evident that Śaivism, though not prior to Buddhism, was once the flourishing religion in the Balasore region of Odisha. And the sculpture of Lakuliśa, excavated from the Kasbā region of Balasore is the earliest available dated monument attesting to the ancientness of Śaivism in Balasore, in particular, and one of the earliest Śaiva monuments of Odisha, in general.

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